

Physico-Chemical Studies of Some Mixed Ligand Complexes of Samarium(III) and Holmium(III)

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Stability constants of mixed ligand complexes of Sm(III) and Ho(III) with cyclohexanediaminetetraacetic acid (CyDTA) as primary ligand and Alizarin Reds (ARS), 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (OSA) or iminodiacetic acid (IMDA) as secondary ligand were determined potentiometrically at 0.05, 0.10, 0.15, 0.20 and 0.25 ionic strengths in aqueous medium at 30°. Ionic strength data are utilized to establish the applicability of Bronsted equation at lower ionic strengths. The thermodynamic stability constants, $\log K_1^H$, $\log K_2^H$ and $\log K_{MAL}^{CYDTA}$ at zero ionic strength are also determined. The influence of solvent media is studied by evaluating stability constants in 25, 40, 50, 60 and 75% dioxan-water mixtures at 30° and 0.1M ionic strength in addition to the study in aqueous medium as mentioned earlier.

THE present communication describes the stability constants of ternary complexes of Sm(III) and Ho(III) with cyclohexanediaminetetraacetic acid (CyDTA) as primary ligand and Alizarin Red S (ARS), 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (OSA) and iminodiacetic acid (IMDA) as secondary ligands in aqueous medium at ionic strengths 0.05, 0.1, 0.15, 0.20 and 0.25 M at 30° and in different compositions of dioxan-water media, 25, 40, 50, 60 and 75% at 0.1 M ionic strength.

Some work have been reported^{1,2} on the influence of ionic strength and dielectric constant of the medium on the stability constant of binary systems. The present study deals with a systematic study of stability constants of some ternary systems (i) in aqueous medium of various ionic strengths and (ii) in dioxan-water mixtures of different compositions. The former study helps in understanding the effect of number of electrolyte ions and the latter gives information about the influence of dielectric constant on the stability of complexes.

The formation constants of mixed-ligand chelates using CyDTA as primary ligand have been determined using Irving-Rossotti pH titration technique³. Recent findings indicate that the rare earth ions^{4,5} are considered to expand their coordination number to larger than six. The assumption of coordination number of eight for Sm(III) and Ho(III) seems to explain the experimental observations more satisfactorily than a coordination number of six in cases of ternary systems, as reported in this paper. The choice of the secondary ligands was done on the basis of different bonding groups present so as to see the effect of different ionic strength and different dielectric constant of media on the protonation constants and stability constants of the ternary systems using them.

Experimental

Materials: All chemicals used were of reagent grade purity. The ligand solutions were prepared

by dissolving ARS (E. Merck), OSA (E. Merck) and IMDA (B.D.H.) in double distilled water. A stock solution of disodium salt of CyDTA (Koch-light) was prepared by dissolving the calculated amount of the acid in the required volume of standardized NaOH solution. Metal solutions were prepared from their chlorides (Indian Rare Earth Ltd.) by dissolving in known quantity of perchloric acid and were estimated complexometrically⁶.

Apparatus: An expanded scale pH-meter (ECIL) with accuracy ± 0.02 pH units was employed to measure pH or 'B' values (pH-meter reading). All experiments were carried out in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The temperature was maintained constant with a ultracryostat bath (MK 70, Germany) having an accuracy of $\pm 0.02^\circ$.

Procedure: For the study of ternary complexes following four mixtures were prepared:

- $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ perchloric acid,
- $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ perchloric acid + $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ secondary ligand,
- $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ perchloric acid + $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ CyDTA solution + $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ metal solution, and
- $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ perchloric acid + $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ CyDTA solution + $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ metal solution + $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ secondary ligand.

In each case total volume was made upto 100 ml by adding required amount of double distilled water or purified dioxan as the case may be. The ionic strength was maintained by adding appropriate amount of neutral sodium perchlorate solution. In all the cases the ratio between metal, CyDTA and secondary ligand was kept 1:1:1. These mixtures were titrated with standardized NaOH. A modified form of Irving-Rossotti titration technique was used for the calculation of $\log K_{MAL}^{CYDTA}$. In case of water-dioxan solvent media,

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AND MIXED-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS IN MEDIUM OF DIFFERENT IONIC STRENGTHS AT 80°

System	Constants	Ionic strength					
		0	0.05	0.10	0.15	0.20	0.25
H-ARS	log K ₁ ^H	11.18	11.06	11.00	10.92	10.82	10.75
	log K ₂ ^H	5.43	5.37	5.33	5.28	5.24	5.21
H-OSA	log K ₁ ^H	8.68	8.52	8.45	8.38	8.30	8.26
	log K ₂ ^H	3.92	3.85	3.78	3.72	3.68	3.65
H-IMDA	log K ₁ ^H	9.52	9.46	9.35	9.27	9.18	9.12
	log K ₂ ^H	2.80	2.74	2.70	2.65	2.62	2.58
[Sm(III)(CyDTA)(ARS)]	log K	6.58	6.44	6.36	6.30	6.25	6.21
[Sm(III)(CyDTA)(OSA)]	log K	3.85	3.75	3.68	3.60	3.54	3.50
[Sm(III)(CyDTA)(IMDA)]	log K	3.40	3.35	3.28	3.20	3.12	3.08
[Ho(III)(CyDTA)(ARS)]	log K	6.86	6.76	6.70	6.63	6.58	6.55
[Ho(III)(CyDTA)(OSA)]	log K	4.36	4.23	4.15	4.08	4.02	3.98
[Ho(III)(CyDTA)(IMDA)]	log K	3.89	3.82	3.75	3.62	3.55	3.50

TABLE 2—PROTON-LIGAND AND MIXED-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS IN DIFFERENT COMPOSITIONS OF DIOXAN-WATER MIXTURES AT FIXED IONIC STRENGTH μ = 0.1M AND T = 80°

System	Constants	Dioxane%					
		0	25	40	50	60	75
H-ARS	log K ₁ ^H	11.00	11.05	11.12	11.21	11.36	11.55
	log K ₂ ^H	5.33	5.38	5.54	5.70	5.92	6.28
H-OSA	log K ₁ ^H	8.45	8.58	8.83	9.06	9.42	9.95
	log K ₂ ^H	3.78	3.82	3.95	4.08	4.27	4.46
H-IMDA	log K ₁ ^H	9.35	9.47	9.62	9.73	9.86	10.12
	log K ₂ ^H	2.70	2.75	2.90	3.04	3.16	3.32
[Sm(III)(CyDTA)(ARS)]	log K	6.36	6.47	6.62	6.75	6.92	7.18
[Sm(III)(CyDTA)(OSA)]	log K	3.68	3.85	4.03	4.16	4.40	4.65
[Sm(III)(CyDTA)(IMDA)]	log K	3.28	3.41	3.55	3.68	3.80	4.06
[Ho(III)(CyDTA)(ARS)]	log K	6.70	6.83	6.95	7.06	7.22	7.53
[Ho(III)(CyDTA)(OSA)]	log K	4.15	4.30	4.45	4.68	4.78	5.08
[Ho(III)(CyDTA)(IMDA)]	log K	3.75	3.86	3.98	4.07	4.24	4.52

the 'B' values were used for the calculation of pL, instead of pH values, where 'B' denotes the pH-meter reading only and not the actual pH, as the pH-meter was calibrated with aqueous buffers. The use of pH meter reading 'B' instead of true pH values did not make any difference^{8,7} in the calculation of free ligand concentration and was usually valid for water-dioxan media.

Results and Discussion

The values of proton-ligand stability and mixed ligand stability constants at different ionic strengths and at 30° are given in Table 1. The thermodynamic stability constants pK₁^o, pK₂^o and log K₁^o, calculated using Bronsted equation at zero ionic strength, are also recorded in this table. Stability constants of various mixed ligand complexes studied and the proton-ligand stability constants of the secondary ligands in mixed solvents of different dielectric constants are summarised in Table 2.

Method of interpolation at various n̄_A or n̄ values was employed for the computation of proton-ligand and mixed ligand stability constants.

The plot of log K_{MAL}^{CyDTA} against √μ and plot of log K_{MAL}^{CyDTA} vs mole fraction of dioxan for [Ho(III)(CyDTA)(L)] systems are represented in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2, respectively. Similar plots for the Sm(III) mixed ligand complexes and the proton-ligand systems were obtained.

Influence of ionic strength on proton-ligand and mixed ligand systems: It may be seen from the data in Table 1 that increase in ionic strength decreases the values of log K₁^H, log K₂^H and log K_{MAL}^{CyDTA}. These data were analyzed by Bronsted equation

$$\log K = \log K^o + A \Delta Z^2 \sqrt{\mu} \quad \dots (1)$$

where A is the Debye-Hückel constant, ΔZ² is the difference in square of the charge of product and reacting ions and K^o is the formation constant at zero ionic strength. The plots of log K₁^H, log K₂^H or log K_{MAL}^{CyDTA} against √μ show almost linear relationship for the entire range of ionic strength.

Fig. 1. A plot of log K against $\sqrt{\mu}$.
 A.A. [Ho(III)CyDTA(ARS)]
 B.B. [Ho(III)CyDTA(OSA)]
 C.C. [Ho(III)CyDTA(IMDA)]

Fig. 2. A plot of log K against mole fraction of dioxan.
 A.A. [Ho(III)(CyDTA)(ARS)]
 B.B. [Ho(III)(CyDTA)(OSA)]
 C.C. [Ho(III)(CyDTA)(IMDA)]

This proves the validity of the Bronsted equation at low ionic strengths.

Influence of dielectric constant : It is seen from Table 2 that $\log K_1^H$, $\log K_2^H$ and $\log K_{MAL}^{CyDTA}$ values increase with percentage increase of dioxan in the mixture, as is well known. The stability constants of mixed ligand complexes are considerably influenced by the dielectric constant of the solvent medium because both primary complex and the secondary ligands are charged. Similarly, there is increase in proton-ligand stability because protons are held by a solvent with a predominant basic property.

It is worthwhile to mention that the experimental evidences of formation of mixed ligand complexes in the present study are also in favour of expansion of coordination number of Sm(III) and Ho(III) in case of mixed ligand complexes with CyDTA acting as primary ligand. The relative order of stability in terms of metal ions is $Ho(III) > Sm(III)$ which can be explained on the basis of decreasing size and increasing charge/radius ratio of the metal ions.

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